
Environmental Responsibility and Sustainable Growth of Listed Industrial Goods Firms in Nigeria

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Abstract

This work empirically investigated the effect of environmental responsibility on sustainable growth of listed industrial goods firms in Nigeria. The study is vital as it portrays the extent to which corporate environmental responsibility influence firms' sustainable growth in Nigeria. In order to determine the relationship between environmental responsibility and firms' sustainable growth, some key proxy variables were used in the study, namely environmental research and development disclosure and waste management disclosure while firm sustainable growth on the hand was measured using sustainable growth rate. Two hypotheses were formulated to guide the investigation and the statistical test of parameter estimates was conducted using Panel least squares regression model. The research design used is Ex Post Facto design and data for the study were obtained from the published annual financial reports of industrial goods firms listed on the floors of the Nigerian Exchange Group (NGX) spanning from 2019-2023. The findings generally indicate that environmental research and development disclosure and waste management disclosure have positive and significant effect on firm sustainable growth in Nigeria at 1% level of significance. Based on this, the study concludes that corporate environmental responsibility ensures sustainable growth of listed industrial goods firms in Nigeria. The study therefore recommends that firms in Nigeria should sustain and also increase the disclosure of their environmental activities in their published financial statements, as it has the potential to positively influence sustainable growth of firms even though it is not mandatory.

Keywords: Environmental Responsibility; Environmental Research and Development Disclosure; Waste Management Disclosure; Sustainable Growth

1. Introduction

A large number of firms in Nigeria are indifferent and lethargic about their environmental responsibility as their operations and activities are not committed to sustainability practices, environmentally friendly operations, openness and sensitivity to environment. Thus resulting to a severe and far-reaching consequences ranging from damage to a company's reputation and brand image, loss of customers patronage and revenue, legal and regulatory actions, vandalization from the host community as a result of not giving back to the community, economic downturn to long term consequences like business closure/bankruptcy. Hence, the present study seeks to investigate if corporate environmental responsibility if committed could ensure firm sustainable growth in Nigeria as the fulfillment of environmental responsibility by companies does not only mean; improving their reputation, but also improving their production processes and enhancing efficiency that can ultimately ensure corporate sustainable growth.

From the a priori expectations (Adegbe, Ogidan, Siyanbola & Adebayo, 2020; Miralles-Quirós, Miralles-Quirós & Hernández, 2021; Paul & Devi, 2022; Servaes & Tamayo, 2023; Oyedokun, Eberioyinemi & Abiola, 2023; Koo, 2024; Klimek, 2024 etc), several stakeholders have expressed concerns over the need for corporate environmental responsibilities to meet their expectations and not much has been done in academic literature in addressing the relationship which exists between corporate environmental responsibilities and firm sustainable growth from the investors' perspective in Nigeria to the best of our knowledge. Also, as the global environmental crisis intensifies, energy supplies and waste management become increasingly tight while the global climate continues to deteriorate; environmental issues therefore receives more and more focused attention and calls for corporate organizations to assume environmental responsibility as they are the main bearer of economic development. Thus, the operations and activities of corporate organizations are bound to have an impact on the environment which calls for their friendly, morally and evenly practices for their long term sustainability growth which stems from stakeholders' theory that a firm has one and only one goal to satisfy the desires of shareholders by making profits but the profit may not be attainable if the environment in which the business operates is neglected. The study therefore seeks to understand if corporate environmental responsibility could ensure corporate sustainable growth other than mere profitability in Nigeria.

None of the a priori expectations in the developing economies limited corporate environmental responsibility to firm sustainable growth to the best of our knowledge using industrial goods firms as a reference point. Hence the need for the present study to examine the relationship which exists between corporate environmental responsibility and sustainable growth of listed industrial goods firms in Nigeria.

To achieve this purpose, we formulated the following hypotheses:

H₀₁: Environmental research and development disclosure has no significant effect on sustainable growth of listed industrial goods firms in Nigeria.

H₀₂: Waste management disclosure does not significantly influence the sustainable growth of listed industrial goods firms in Nigeria.

2. Review of the Related Literature

2.1.1 Environmental Responsibility (ER)

Bai and Meng (2023) opine that environmental responsibility is a reasonable and legal decision and concrete social action by companies to achieve their own goals and corporate values through corresponding government policies. Also, Klassen and McLaughlin (2022) reported that environmental responsibility is a due obligation for companies, i.e. companies must give back to society when they use natural resources for economic benefits in order to achieve long-term corporate development. Xiaohong, Zhang and Huixiang (2022) state that environmental responsibility essentially means that companies should follow a sustainable development perspective, consume fewer resources and produce less waste in their production processes. In terms of the concept of corporate environmental responsibility, it refer to the process of reducing the consumption of natural resources in the operation of a company, reducing the level of environmental load on various wastes and thus achieving sustainable development

According to Pang, Shang and Weng (2021), environmental responsibility consists of two aspects: firstly, energy saving, which reduces the demand on the environment. The second is the reduction of emissions, reducing the discharge of waste in the environment. The study also goes further to note that corporate environmental responsibility is the actions taken by companies to meet environmental ethical and legal requirements in order to achieve environmental sustainability. Environmental responsibility, a manifest of environmental sustainability is the duty and environmentally managerial tools, which the enterprises employ to operate their business towards to protecting and improving surrounding environments (Holtbrügge & Dögl, 2022). In the study of Quang (2020), environmental responsibility was deemed as a fundamental aspect of managing sustainability and social responsibility. Environmental, social and economic aspects are three main sides of sustainability reflecting sustainable growth of enterprises; where environmental side or environmental responsibility has been broadly considered to play a growingly imperative role in organizational strategies and environmental and economic performance of the enterprises.

For the purpose of this study, environmental responsibility was proxied using environmental research and development and waste management disclosure. This is discussed below as thus:

2.1.1.1 Environmental Research and Development Disclosure (ERDD)

The scheme for environmental research and development was initiated for promoting and initiating need based environmental research in the priority areas of pollution monitoring, disaster management mitigation, low cost waste treatment, river/lake water quality monitoring, solid waste management, climate change studies and other need based areas, and this programme is being carried out (Oyedokun, Eberioyinemi & Abiola, 2023).

Environmental research and development disclosure (ERDD) is a disclosure on the activities that companies undertake to innovate and introduce new products and services. It is often the first stage in the development process. The goal is typically to take new products and services to market and add to the company's bottom line (Adegbe, Ogidan, Siyanbola & Adebayo, 2020).

According to Domenico (2024) environmental research and development disclosure is a disclosure on the process of promoting sustainable and responsible use of natural resources

while mitigating negative impacts on the environment and ecosystems for a healthier and resilient planet and world. It involves the study and creation of innovative technologies aimed at solving environmental challenges and promoting sustainability. This field encompasses a wide range of activities, including developing renewable energy sources, improving waste management systems, enhancing pollution control measures, and creating sustainable agricultural practices. The study therefore notes that the goal is to develop technologies that reduce environmental impact, conserve natural resources, and promote a healthier planet.

2.1.1.2 Waste Management Disclosure (WMD)

A waste management system is a streamlined process that organizations use to dispose of, reduce, reuse, and prevent waste. Also known as waste disposal, it is an approach where companies implement comprehensive strategies to efficiently manage wastes from their origin until their final disposal (Agyemang, Yusheng, Twun, Edziah & Ayamba, 2021)

According to Fizzah, Fangjun, Jiyuan and Mohammed (2023), waste management refers to the processes involved in managing waste from cradle to grave. This includes the collection, transportation, disposal/recycling and monitoring of waste materials produced as a result of human activity. The study notes that the new methods of waste disposal to include; landfill, incineration, waste compaction, composting, vermicomposting.

Waste is defined as any substance or article which constitutes a scrap material or an effluent or other surplus substances arising from application of any process (Environmental Protection Authority, 2020). Waste management is an overall approach to prevent waste and it combines a range of collection and treatment methods to handle all materials in the waste stream in an environmentally effective, economically affordable and socially acceptable way (Klassen & McLaughlin, 2022).

2.1.2 Sustainable Growth

According to Tutun and Som (2019), sustainable growth is a growth that could be profitably maintained for future benefits. Sustainable growth as a concept was popularized by Higgins' remarkable study in 1977, where he proposed that sustainable growth rate model should be used to explain its practical limits to growing firms. Therefore, sustainable growth rate explains if there is consistency between the sales growth with the realities of the firm and the financial market. As reported by Omaliko et al. (2023), corporate sustainable growth is all about the financial performance information and non-financial performance information that includes social and environmental activities that enable firms to grow sustainably and friendly.

The study of Omaliko et al. (2025), Ezeala et al. (2024), submitted that to ensure sustainable growth, organizations must concede the following:

- i. Responsible for their social, environmental and economic impact.
- ii. Being transparent in decisions and activities affecting its responsibilities.
- iii. Interests of the stakeholders to be responded to.
- iv. The rule of law is mandatory for all.

A firm with growth rate which deviates from sustainable growth will eventually fall into the dilemma of unsustainable growth (Buffa, Franch & Rizio, 2020). For the purpose of this study, sustainable growth was measured as return on equity multiplied by retention ratio. This is expressed as ROE (1-DPR).

2.3 Theoretical Framework

The theoretical framework which gives the meaning of a word in terms of the theories on corporate environmental responsibility and firm sustainable growth established in this study is Stakeholder Theory. It assumes that both the knowledge and acceptance of this theory that this study depends upon.

2.3.1 Stakeholder Theory

The theoretical foundation of this paper is anchored on the Stakeholders Theory. The theory was propounded by Freeman in the year 1984. The stakeholder theory postulates that the firm does not operate as an island, but its success depends on multiple stakeholders who have different interest on the firm's operations. This means that the firm has to identify these stakeholders (employees, customers, suppliers, local community, government and so on) who can influence the firm's outcomes. Also, the stakeholder theory sees corporate organizations as the elements of the social system or group where the firm's success is dependent upon the successful management of all the relationships that a firm has with its stakeholders; those groups without whose support the organization would cease to exist (Freeman, 1984).

On this note, Obey (2020) notes that it is not sufficient for managers to focus exclusively on the needs of stockholders, or the owners of the business. This implies that it can be beneficial for the firm to engage in certain environmental activities that non-financial stakeholders perceive important, because without this, these groups might withdraw their support from the business. According to Onyali, Okafor and Onodi (2015), stakeholders' theory proposed an increased level of environmental and social awareness which creates the need for companies to manage these interests (groups' interest) in order for them to become environmentally friendly and social responsible towards the environment in which the business is domiciled. The main concern of the stakeholders' theory in environmental accounting is to address the environmental disclosure elements and valuation and its inclusion in the financial statements for external users consumption.

In this era of sustainability, corporate environmental responsibility has unique roles to play to ensure that the firm attains its sustainability goals. Performing poorly on this can hinder firms from attaining desired milestones in sustainable development (Obey, 2020). Dodson, Azevedo, Mohiuddin, Defavari and Abrahão (2015) assert that organizations should do stakeholder analysis in order to identify key environmental issues in the organization which should not be neglected or overemphasized. Stakeholder analysis therefore assists a firm to clearly identify and manage different needs of the environment in order to avoid future conflicts and lawsuits. Also, Dodson, *et al.* (2015) noted that stakeholder analysis is important as it accommodates special cases such as the natural environment, which is in most cases, neglected because it does not reflect in company financial statements. Summarily, the stakeholder theory illustrates that the firm has one and only one goal to satisfy the desires of shareholders by making profits. However, profit may not be attainable if the environment in which the business operates is neglected.

Thus, this study is anchored on stakeholders' theory. The justification for using this theory to underpin the study stem from the fact that literature review has demonstrated the existence of relationship between the environmental responsibility, corporate performance and corporate sustainable growth.

2.3 Empirical Review

Uyagu, Joshua, Terzungwe and Muhammad (2024) examined the effect of firm characteristics on environmental reporting practices of listed manufacturing firms in Nigeria. The population of the study comprises of sixty-one (61) manufacturing firms with a sample size of 29 firms drawn using judgmental sampling technique. Data were gathered using annual reports and accounts of the sampled firms through content analysis and analysed using multiple regression technique. The study found that firm size, leverage, return on assets and firm age have significant and positive effect on environmental reporting practices of listed manufacturing firms in Nigeria. The study therefore concludes that firm characteristics have positive effect on corporate

Domenico (2024) examined the relationship between corporate environmental responsibility and corporate performance in Italy. The study used samples from Italian firms and suggests a weak positive association between corporate environmental responsibility and financial performance. The study explored the statistical tool of regression model and concludes that corporate environmental responsibility disclosure has no significant effect on financial performance of firms measured by ROE in Italy.

Zhenghui, Gaoke and Khaldoun (2024) evaluated the relationship between corporate environmental responsibility (CER) engagement and firm value as well as exploring the mediating effect of corporate innovation on this relationship based on a sample of 496 China's A-share listed companies from 2014 to 2022. Using OLS, the results show that when firms start to adopt environmental regulations, CER would have a negative effect on firm value, however at a specific level, CER would start to enhance firm value positively. In addition to this, corporate innovation plays a mediating role in the relationship between CER and firm value. Corporate innovation promotes firm value of firms with CER more than firms without CER.

Rabiu, Yazid and Muhammad (2023) examined the effect of environmental reporting on financial performance of listed Nigerian industrial and consumer goods firms for the period of ten (10) years from 2012 to 2021. The population of the study comprises forty-two (42) listed industrial and consumer goods firms in Nigeria. Eleven (11) firms were selected as the study sample size, which comprises 5 industrial goods and 6 consumer goods firms. The study used return on asset (ROA) as a proxy for financial performance. Secondary data were used and extracted from the firm's annual reports of the firms under review. Using regression model, the result revealed that environmental information has significant positive effect on return on asset (ROA); employee health and safety have negative significant effect on ROA; product safety has negative significant effect on ROA. Based on these findings, this study therefore, concludes that environmental reporting influence financial performance of listed industrial and consumer goods firms in Nigeria.

Bassey, Sunday and Okon (2023) examined the impact of environmental accounting and reporting on organizational performance with particular reference to oil and gas companies operating in the Niger Delta Region of Nigeria. The study was conducted using the Pearson's product moment correlation co-efficient. The elements were selected by means of random

and stratified sampling technique. Data were gathered from primary and secondary sources. Data collected were presented using tables and analyzed using the Pearson's product moment correlational analysis. It was found from the study that environmental cost has satisfied relationship with firm's profitability. It was concluded that environmentally friendly firms will significantly disclose environmental related information in financial statements and reports.

Fizzah, Fangjun, Jiyuan and Mohammed (2023) examined the impact of environmental disclosure on financial performance mediating the impact of green innovation by provide novel evidence regarding this relationship using stakeholder and signalling theory. This study used a sample dataset comprising Chinese firms listed on Shanghai and Shenzhen stock exchange for the period of 2011–2022. In our measurement model, green innovation is the partial mediator between the positive relationship of environmental disclosure and firm performance. Using regression model, the empirical results show that environmental disclosure affects firm financial performance directly and positively influences it through green innovation in Chinese firms. The study suggests that Chinese firms have implications for improved performance by increasing environmental disclosure and green practices.

Akinpelu, Ogunbi, Olaniran and Ogunseye (2023) investigated the various types of environmental responsibility activities information that were disclosed by Nigerian commercial banks and the factors that determine the level of disclosure in their annual reports and accounts. Descriptive data analysis results indicated that commercial banks in Nigeria disclosed more information on human resources and community involvement and very low information on environmental, product quality and consumer relation. The outcome of multivariate analysis suggested that value of total assets have positive relationship and statistically significant with the level of corporate environmental responsibility activities disclosure, although, gross earnings and number of branches are positively and significantly related with corporate environmental responsibility disclosure level.

Olusola (2023) investigated the nexus between corporate environmental responsibilities and financial performance within the oil, gas, mineral, and metal mining sector. Aiteo Groups and Sahara Groups are utilized as case studies to probe the influence of environmental policies on financial performance. Employing financial metrics such as return on equity, return on assets, and stock market performance and regression model, the results reveal a nuanced relationship between the financial performance of Aiteo Group and Sahara Group and their commitment to corporate environmental responsibility. The results showed that managers' environmental attitude is a good predictor of corporate reputation, with R squared and adjusted R squared of 0.519 and 0.489 respectively and a significant linear relationship at the 1% level. While a positive correlation is identified between financial performance and robust environmental practices, there is evidence that short-term financial performance may be negatively impacted by environmental activities. Environmental, social, and governance (ESG) factors should be integrated into investment choices, as these studies highlight.

3. Methodology

An *ex post facto* design was used in the study based on the fact that the data for the study was secondary which already existed and cannot be controlled. The population of the study consists of 13 listed industrial goods firms on Nigerian Exchange Group (NGX) as at December 31, 2023, covering the period 2019-2023. The data was collected from the annual accounts and annual accounts of the sampled firms. Panel least square regression model was

used to examine the relationship between environmental responsibility and sustainable growth of listed industrial goods firms in Nigeria.

3.1 Measurement and Operationalization of Variables

A dichotomous procedure by (GRI) was applied in scoring the items of (environmental research & development disclosure and waste management disclosure) whereby specifically, a “1-point” score was awarded for each item reported in the annual report and otherwise, a “0-point”. Then, the sum of scores of all items for each of the class of disclosure was computed. Therefore, the ERDD and WMD score for the company is derived by calculating the actual sum of scores awarded to a company to a maximum of 5 years. The dependent variable (sustainable growth) on the other hand was measured using ROE(1-DPR) in line with the previous studies.

3.2 Model Specification and Justification

In line with the previous researches, the present study designed a model in determining the effect of environmental responsibility on sustainable growth of listed industrial goods firms in Nigeria. The functional model for the study is therefore shown below as thus:

$$SG = F(ERDD, WMD)$$

The explicit form of the regression designed for the study is expressed as thus:

$$SG_{it} = \beta_0 + \beta_1 ERDD_{it} + \beta_2 WMD_{it} + \mu$$

Where:

SG = Sustainable Growth

ERDD= Environmental Research and Development Disclosure

WMD= Waste Management Disclosure

μ = Stochastic Term

$\beta_1 - \beta_2$ = Coefficient of Regression Equation

β_0 = Constant coefficient (intercept) of the model

Decision Rule: accept H_0 if P-value > 1%-5% significant level otherwise reject H_0

4. Data Analysis and Results

Table 1: Descriptive Statistics

	SG	ERDD	WMD
Mean	0.17	4.37	3.96
Median	0.14	4.56	4.10
Maximum	0.77	5.00	5.00
Minimum	0.01	0.00	0.00
Std. Dev.	0.13	0.31	0.36
Skewness	2.92	0.25	-0.71
Kurtosis	2.48	1.39	2.05
Jarque-Bera	310.3	0.53	0.61
Probability	0.34	0.88	0.73
Sum	10.51	24.9	19.8
Sum Sq. Dev.	1.03	0.52	0.53
Observations	65	65	65

Source: E-View 12 Computational Results (2025)

From Table 1 above, the mean (average), maximum values, minimum values, standard deviation and Jarque-Bera Statistics (Normality Test) were shown. The results provide some insight into the nature of the listed industrial goods firms in Nigeria used in this study. First, it can be observed that on the average, in a 5-year period (2019-2023), the sampled firms were characterized by a positive sustainable growth (SG) value of 0.17. This implies that SG of listed industrial firms in Nigeria is determined by environmental disclosures. Thus, environmental disclosures ensure firm sustainable growth in Nigeria. The distribution is platykurtic since the kurtosis (2.48) is less than 3, implying that the outliers are few. The Jarque-Bera probability of 0.34 is greater than 0.05, which means that the distribution of sustainable growth comes from a normal distribution. The average value of environmental research and development disclosure (ERDD) for the sampled firms was 4.37 with a standard deviation value of 0.31. This means that firms with ERDD values of 4.37 and above are environmental responsive. There is also a high variation in maximum and minimum values of ERDD which stood at 5.00 and 0.00 respectively. This wide variation in ERDD values among the sampled firms justifies the need for this study that environmental research and development disclosure ensures firm sustainable growth in Nigeria. The distribution is platykurtic since the kurtosis (1.39) is less than 3, implying that the outliers are few. The Jarque-Bera probability of 0.88 is greater than 0.05, which means that the distribution of environmental research and development disclosure comes from a normal distribution.

The mean value of waste management disclosure (WMD) for the sampled firms was 3.96. This means that firms with WMD values of 3.96 and above are environmental responsive. Thus, waste management disclosure ensures firm sustainable growth in Nigeria. There is also a high variation in maximum and minimum values of WMD which stood at 5.00 and 0.00 respectively. This wide variation in WMD values among the sampled firms justifies the need for this study that waste management disclosure ensures firm sustainable growth at a degree risk of 0.36%. The distribution is platykurtic since the kurtosis (2.05) is less than 3, implying that the outliers are few. The Jarque-Bera probability of 0.73 is greater than 0.05, which means that the distribution of waste management disclosure does not deviate from normal distribution.

In an effort to establish the nature of the correlation between the dependent and the independent variables and also to ascertain whether or not multi-collinearity exists as a result of the correlation between the variables, table 2 was incorporated which provides an insights into the nature and extent of correlation among the independent variables and how they are related to the dependent variable.

Table 2: Correlation Matrix

Variables	NAPS	ESD	SSD	CGD
<i>SG</i>	1.0000			
<i>ERDD</i>	0.1077	1.0000		
<i>WMD</i>	0.0647	-0.0918	1.0000	

Source: E-View 12 Computational Results (2024).

Table 2 above shows the relationship between all pairs of independent variables and dependent variable used in the regression model. It reveals that all the independent variables have positive correlation with the dependent variable (SG) while some of these components of environmental responsibility have negative relationship with one another. The values on the diagonal are all 1.0000 which shows that each variable is perfectly correlated with itself. In checking for multi-collinearity, we noticed that no two explanatory variables were perfectly correlated. This means that there is an absence of multi-collinearity in our model.

4.1: Test of Hypothesis

Table 3: Result on Effect of Environmental Responsibility on Sustainable Growth of Firms in Nigeria.

Dependent Variable: SG
 Method: Panel Least Squares
 Date: 04/23/25 Time: 11:58
 Sample: 2019 -2023
 Periods included: 5
 Cross-sections included: 13
 Total panel (balanced) observations: 65

Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistic	Prob.
ERDD	0.408994	0.105913	3.861603	0.0024
WMD	0.336601	0.075133	4.480092	0.0000
C	0.133516	0.031571	4.427409	0.0000
R-squared	0.757441	Mean dependent var		1.028979
Adjusted R-squared	0.729419	S.D. dependent var		3.015098
S.E. of regression	2.939653	Akaike info criterion		5.006985
Sum squared resid	2030.766	Schwarz criterion		5.050753
Log likelihood	592.8312	Hannan-Quinn criter.		5.024624
F-statistic	7.160587	Durbin-Watson stat		2.230972
Prob(F-statistic)	0.000958			

Source: E-View 12 Computational Results (2024).

4.2: Discussion of Findings.

The coefficient of determination R^2 shows 0.76 indicating that the overall model explained 76 percent of the total variations in the dependent variable. Thus shows that these variables (ERDD & WMD) can only explain 76 percent of change in firms' sustainable growth leaving 24 percent unexplained. This is to say that there are other factors that could led to firm sustainable growth other than environmental responsibilities. The sig. (or p-value) is .0000 which is below the .01 level; hence, we conclude that the overall model is statistically significant, or that the variables have a significant combined or joint effect on the dependent variable. With this, the researcher affirms the validity of the regression model adopted in this study.

The results of the regression are therefore slated below as follows:

H₀₁: Environmental research and development disclosure has no significant effect on sustainable growth of listed industrial goods firms in Nigeria.

This hypothesis was tested and the result of this regression as expositied on table 3 indicates that the relationship between ERDD and SG is positive and significant; this can be justified with the P-value (significance) of 0.0024 which is less than the 1% level of significance adopted. Likewise the result of positive coefficient of 0.409 indicates that environmental research and development disclosure ensures firm sustainable growth in Nigeria. Thus, implies that environmental research and development disclosure determines firm sustainable growth in Nigeria. We therefore accepted the alternate hypothesis which contends that environmental research and development disclosure has significant effect on sustainable growth of listed industrial firms in Nigeria.

This aligns with the a priori expectations of Uyagu, Joshua, Terzungwe and Muhammad (2024), Zhenghui, Gaoke and Khaldoon (2024) who found positive and significant association between corporate environmental disclosures and firm performance.

H₀₂: Waste management disclosure does not significantly influence the sustainable growth of listed industrial goods firms in Nigeria.

This hypothesis was tested and the result of this regression as expositied on table 3 indicates that the relationship between WMD and SG is positive and significant; this can be justified with the P-value (significance) of 0.0000 which is less than the 1% level of significance adopted. Likewise the result of positive coefficient of 0.337 indicates that an increase in corporate environmental activities ensures firm sustainable growth in Nigeria. We consequently accepted the alternate hypothesis which contends that waste management disclosure has significant effect on sustainable growth of listed industrial firms in Nigeria.

This is in tandem with the findings of Domenico (2024), Bassey, Sunday and Okon (2023), Fizzah, Fangjun, Jiyuan and Mohammed (2023) who reported positive relationship between corporate environmental reporting and firm performance.

5. Conclusion and Recommendation

The study from the statistical analysis notes that corporate environmental responsibility has positive and significant effect on sustainable growth of listed industrial goods firms in Nigeria. Hence, the study concludes that corporate environmental responsibility ensures

sustainable growth of listed industrial goods firms in Nigeria. The study therefore recommends that firms in Nigeria should sustain and also increase the disclosure of their environmental activities in their published financial statements, as it has the potential to positively influence sustainable growth of firms even though it is not mandatory.

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